

INFLUENCE OF HOME-GROWN SCHOOL FEEDING PROGRAMME ON PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS' ENROLMENT AND ATTENDANCE IN ADAMAWA STATE

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Abstract

The study was conducted to determine the influence of home-grown school feeding programme on primary school pupils' enrolment and attendance in Adamawa State. Two objectives guided the study, the objectives were translated into two research questions and two null hypotheses corresponding with the research questions. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and paired sample t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Ex-post factor research design was used for the study. The study was done in Adamawa State of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 1,331 primary schools implementing the home-grown school feeding programme in Adamawa State. Stratified random sampling technique was used to obtain a sample of 297 primary schools. Data for the study was obtained using a proforma titled "School Record Inventory (SRI)". Face and content validity of the instrument was determined by experts in agricultural education. The instrument was subjected to field trial test using test re-test method in Taraba State. The reliability of the instrument was calculated using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient and a reliability of 0.78 was obtained. The data for the study was collected through the administration of the questionnaire to the primary schools. Results from the study revealed that home grown school feeding programme has improved pupils' enrolment and attendance in primary schools, results also revealed that there is significant difference in the enrolment rate before and after commencement of home-grown school feeding programme. Based on the findings of the study, recommendations were made among which: the federal government should sustain the home-grown school feeding programme because of the increase in enrolment rate of pupils.

Keywords: Home-Grown School Feeding Programme, Primary School, Enrolment, Attendance

Introduction

The role of education in the development of any society cannot be rivaled. Education is basic and obvious process by which skills, knowledge and attitude are acquired for improving personal competencies and seeking better opportunities. Education is generally regarded as the bedrock of human total development (Eluwa & Ihechu, 2020). This is an indication that education is the most powerful instrument that drives citizens' participation in the socio-economic growth and provides a positive change in themselves, society and nation at large. Furthermore, education helps in the positive development of human potentials, talents, intellect, attitude and skills. According to Samuel (2021), education is the foundation of a successful career, ability to think and reason critically so as to make the right decisions. This educational foundation begins with children education which is globally valued and recognized as a basic human right for every child.

Hunger has been a barrier to primary education to many children in low income households in many countries such as Nigeria. Adamawa State is among the low income generating states in Nigeria where hunger and poverty affects primary education. Low enrolment, attendance, poor academic achievement and high rate of learners' drop out made up the barriers to the education of children especially in the areas of high food insecurity. According to Usman (2015), poverty has contributed to the large number of out-of-school children in Nigeria. He viewed poverty as individual inability to live a simple and comfortable life due to lack of access to basic means of early survival which includes; food, shelter, steady income, clothing, education and other basic needs of life. He stressed that poverty has a devastating effect on people and thereby creating an imbalance in the social system. Taiwo and Agwu (2016) posits that poverty makes people live below the recognized minimum living standard. Rais et al (2021) observed that quite a number of primary school age children are roaming on the streets begging or hawking for survival due to poverty at the expense of their primary education.

School feeding programme where it has been implemented showed a strong correlation with pupils' commitment to learning. Specifically, Ramadhani (2014) reported that provision of school based meal to pupils increased their ability to enroll into school and attend school regularly in Tanzania. Gbolagade (2020) asserted that the programme is an intervention which tries to reduce hunger among pupils with the view to improve enrolment, retention, concentration and reduction of dropout rates in primary schools. Provision of school meal serves as incentive to parents which make them enroll their children in school. School feeding off sets the indirect cost of education that parents are supposed to pay for their children (Oyefade, 2014).

In realization of the important role of nutrition to the child and education in Nigeria, the country was among the 12 pilot countries invited to implement school feeding programme which was officially inaugurated on the 19th of June, 2016 (Adepoju & Johnson, 2020). The programme aimed to improve primary school pupils' enrolment and attendance among others. It is against this background this study was carried out to access the Impact of Home-Grown School Feeding Programme on Primary School Pupils' enrolment and attendance in Adamawa State.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of out-of-school children has been of grave concern in Nigeria. Despite the initiatives undertaken by government and non-governmental organizations. In Nigeria, many school age children are not in school. Nigeria has one of the largest out - of - schoolchildren figures in the world. The country is ranked 5th in the World with about 10.19 million out-of-school children and this figure accounts for 34% of the total children population in the country. Most of the children that made up the out-of-school children in Nigeria are found in the north-western region of the country, making up 34.24% of the total out of school children in the country. The north-east with Adamawa State inclusive had 19.63% of the total out-of-school children and the state is second in the region. The south-east has the least proportion with about 7% of the total figure (Temitope et al., 2020). Nnamdi (2014) explains that in Nigeria, children are used for economic viability by some parents by engaging them in economic activities to the extent that they are denied the acquisition of any form of education. Parents feel that their children should be used for making money rather than sending them to schools. Poor enrolment and retention of children in schools is due to family unwillingness to provide the basic materials and also make children available for admission into primary school. Despite the relevant role home grown school feeding programme plays in

encouraging children to go to school, there are numerous challenges that emanate from the whole process which range from low enrolment and absenteeism among others, hence the study.

Purpose of the Study

The study was conducted mainly to assess the influence of home-grown school feeding programme on primary school pupils' enrolment and attendance in Adamawa state. The specific objectives include to:

1. Determine the influence of home-grown school feeding programme on the enrolment rate of primary school pupils in Adamawa State.
2. Determine the influence of home-grown school feeding programme on the attendance rate of primary school pupils in Adamawa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered by the study:

1. What is the enrolment rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of home-grown school feeding programme in Adamawa State?
2. What is the attendance rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of home-grown school feeding programme in Adamawa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 significance level:

- HO₁:** There is no significant difference in the enrolment rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of the HGSFP in Adamawa State.
- HO₂:** There is no significant difference in the attendance rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of the HGSFP in Adamawa State.

Methodology

The study used Ex-post factor research design. The study was conducted in Adamawa State of Nigeria. There are 1,331 primary schools implementing the home-grown school feeding programme in Adamawa State making up the population for the study. Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for determining sample size was used to obtain a sample of 297 primary schools. Data for the study was obtained using a proforma titled "School Record Inventory (SRI)" The instrument was used to collect school records on enrolment and attendance. Validation of the instrument was done by experts in agricultural education with one from the Department of Vocational Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola and the other one from The Department of Science Education, Federal University of Kashere, Gombe. The instrument was subjected to field trial test using test re-test method in Taraba State. The instrument's reliability was calculated using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient and a reliability of 0.78 was obtained. The data used for the study was collected by the researchers from primary schools in the study area. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer all the research questions and decision rule was based on the difference in the mean on enrolment rate and attendance rate

before and after commencement of HGSFP. Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level using paired sample t-test.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the enrolment rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of home-grown school feeding programme in Adamawa State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Enrolment Rate of Primary School Pupils before and after Commencement of Home-Grown School Feeding Programme in Adamawa State

	N	Mean	SD
Enrolment before HGSFP	297	20494.47	3343.14503
Enrolment after HGSFP	297	29945.00	5365.72698

The Table 1 presents results of analysis on the enrolment rate of pupils in primary schools in Adamawa State before and after commencement of the home-grown school feeding programme. The sample size for both periods consisted of 297 schools. Before the programme, the mean enrolment rate was approximately 20,494.47 pupils in primary one, two and three, while after the programme, this figure increased significantly to approximately 29,945.00 primary school pupils on the average. This substantial increase in enrolment rates after the programme commencement suggests a positive impact, indicating that more children enrolled into primary school following the commencement of the programme. However, the standard deviation, which measures the variability in enrolment rates among the schools, also increased after the programme commenced, indicating a greater spread in the data. To draw more definitive conclusions about the program's effectiveness, further statistical analysis, such as hypothesis testing, would be necessary to assess whether this increase is statistically significant and to understand the programme's true impact on primary school enrolment in Adamawa State.

Research Question 2: What is the attendance rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of home-grown school feeding programme in Adamawa State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Attendance Rate of Primary School Pupils before and after Commencement of Home-Grown School Feeding Programme in Adamawa State

	N	Mean	SD
Attendance before HGSFP	297	18705.33	3068.78046
Attendance after HGSFP	297	29571.07	5354.53868

Results of analysis in Table 2 provides the mean and standard deviation on the attendance rate of pupils in Adamawa State primary schools both before and after the commencement of the programme. The data set encompasses primary one to three pupils in 297 primary school, ensuring a representative sample for analysis. Before the programme commencement, mean attendance rate stood at approximately 18,705.33 primary school pupils, with a standard deviation of approximately 3,068.78046, which indicates the variability in attendance rates across the classes in the sampled primary schools. After the programme introduction, the mean attendance rate surged to approximately 29,571.07 in the 297 primary

schools. This substantial increase in attendance rates after the program suggests a significant positive impact. The standard deviation also increased to approximately 5,354.53868 after the programme was introduced indicating a broader dispersion of attendance rates among the schools.

Overall, the result indicates a notable improvement in primary school attendance rates following the programme implementation in Adamawa State. However, the increased standard deviation suggests that while attendance rates improved on average, there may be variations in the degree of improvement across different schools.

Hypothesis One

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the enrolment rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of the HGSFP in Adamawa State.

Table 3: Summary of Paired Sample t – test of Difference in the Enrolment Rate of Primary School Pupils before and after Commencement of Home-Grown School Feeding Programme in Adamawa State

	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p-value	Decision
Enrolment before	297	20494.47	3343.15	296	-7.911	0.000	HO₁ rejected
Enrolment after	297	29945.00	5365.73				

Table 3 summarizes the results of a paired sample t-test conducted to assess whether there is a significant difference in the enrolment rate of primary school pupils before and after the commencement of the HGSFP in Adamawa State. The analysis included data from 297 schools at primary level in the state. Before the HGSFP, the mean enrolment rate was approximately 20,494.47 primary school pupils, with a SD of approximately 3,343.15. After the program's implementation, the mean enrolment rate increased to approximately 29,945.00 primary school pupils, with a standard deviation of approximately 5,365.73. The paired sample t-test yielded a t-value of -7.911 and a p-value of 0.000. When comparing the p-value to a commonly used significance level (e.g., 0.05), it is evident therefore that the p-value is significantly smaller. In this case, the p-value is smaller than 0.05, which is an indication that there is a statistically significant difference between the enrolment rates before and after the commencement of HGSFP. Therefore, based on the paired sample t-test result, the null hypothesis (HO₁) is rejected. This implies that there is indeed a significant difference in enrolment rates of primary school pupils before and after the commencement of the HGSFP in Adamawa State. The programme appears to have had a notable impact on increasing the enrolment of pupils in primary schools in the state.

Hypothesis Two

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the attendance rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of the HGSFP in Adamawa State.

Table 4: Summary of Paired Sample t – test of Difference in the Attendance Rate of Primary School Pupils before and after Commencement of Home-Grown School Feeding Programme in Adamawa State

	N	Mean	SD	df	T	p-value	Decision
Attendance before	297	18705.33	3068.78	296	-8.914	0.000	HO₂
Attendance after	297	29571.07	5354.54				rejected

Table 4 provides result of paired sample t-test designed to determine if significant difference exist in the attendance rate of primary school pupils before and after the commencement of the home-grown school feeding programme (HGSFP) in Adamawa State. In the analysis, data from 297 primary schools in Adamawa State were considered. Before the HGSFP commenced, the mean attendance rate was approximately 18,705.33 primary school pupils, with a standard deviation of approximately 3,068.78. After the programme's implementation, the mean attendance rate increased in its mean to approximately 29,571.07 primary school pupils, with a standard deviation of approximately 5,354.54. The t-test produced a t-value of -8.914 and a p-value of 0.000. When comparing the p-value to a 0.05, it is obvious that the p-value is substantially smaller. Specifically, the p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference between the attendance rates before and after the implementation of the HGSFP. Consequently, based on the results of the t-test, the null hypothesis (HO₂) is rejected. This suggests that there is indeed a significant difference in the attendance rates of primary school pupils before and after the commencement of the HGSFP in Adamawa State. The programme appears to have had a considerable impact on increasing the attendance of pupils in primary schools in the state.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the study revealed that HGSFP has increased enrolment rate of primary school pupils. Food served as incentive for children of primary school age to enrol in school. Hypothesis one was rejected as the null hypothesis revealed that there is significant difference in the enrolment rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of HGSFP. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Igboji et al (2022) who found out in their study that school meal has improved enrolment of pupils in primary schools. In agreement with this finding, Oyefade (2014) also found out in his study that free meal has increase the enrolment of pupils most especially girls in primary schools. Similarly, Elijah and Fredrich (2015) in their study also found out that there was a phenomenal increase in the rate of enrolment due to the introduction of the programme.

This finding implies that HGSFP has made a significant impact on primary school pupils' enrolment and if sustained, the programme is capable of drastically reducing the number of out-of-school children in Adamawa state and Nigeria at large, thereby reducing the rate at which school age children are found hawking or begging on the streets or engaged in child labour or trafficking at the expense of their primary education. With the increase in enrolment, the government is also responsible for building more structures such as classrooms to cater for the increasing population and also, recruitment of competent teachers to meet up with the educational needs of the pupils.

The findings of the study also revealed that there is increase in the attendance rate of the primary school pupils due to the introduction of the HGSFP. Hypothesis two showed that there is significant difference in the attendance rate of primary school pupils before and after commencement of the HGSFP. This finding is supported by that of Solomon and

Yusuf (2022) who found out in their study that the HGSFP encouraged pupils to attend school regularly as there was a drop in the rate of absenteeism among pupils. Awojobi and Tinubu (2020) in agreement with the finding from this study also found out in their study that school meal attract pupils to school and pupils come to school all the time. They further observed that pupils don't absent themselves from school because of the meal served in school.

Conclusion

Primary education is important to the whole system of education in Nigeria. It is the foundation on which all other levels of education are built upon. It is very germane to the success of other levels of education as it provides the basics required to enter into secondary education and subsequently higher or tertiary education. This study found out that food plays an important role in attracting school age children to school and also help them to remain in school in Adamawa State.

Recommendation

The following recommendation were made based on findings from the study:

1. The federal government should sustain the HGSFP because of the increase in enrolment rate of pupils.
2. The HGSFP should be sustained by the government at federal level due to the increase recorded on the attendance rate of pupils in primary schools.

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